

Viewpoint

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Enhancing the Accessibility of Science at *The Lancet* with Native Language Abstracts

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Abstract

Today, 98% of peer-reviewed scientific publishing is in English, which is also the official language of most scientific events and international academic journals. UNESCO, through its Recommendation on Open Science, has called on scientific institutions to foster multilingualism in the practice of science, in scientific publications, and in academic communications. At *The Lancet*, we recognize the need to provide more equitable and inclusive access to scientific knowledge by providing abstracts translated into relevant languages. Following a pilot, a workflow for abstract translation was devised. I present here details of our abstract translation procedure and rollout.

Keywords:

abstract translations, multilingualism, scientific abstracts

Introduction

Around 1800, the Royal Society of London began to use the term ‘abstract’ to describe the summary of a paper written in the minute books by the secretary after a paper had been read aloud at a meeting (the word ‘summary’ is also used nowadays, as it is at *The Lancet*, but it means essentially the same thing). Abstracts occupied less space in the minute books than the full paper, could be read more quickly, and were quicker and cheaper to print, enabling rapid communication of scientific results.¹ Many of the full versions of these papers were later published in the society’s main journal, *Philosophical Transactions*. Until the 1830s, the editorial committee usually worked from the abstracts and only rarely scrutinized the full manuscript, but this approach changed with the introduction of refereeing.^{1,2}

In 1831, the Royal Society began to publish the abstracts ahead of the publication of their journal, *Philosophical Transactions*, in a monthly journal, *Proceedings of the Royal Society*. To ease the burden on the society’s secretaries, author-generated abstracts were first formally requested from authors in 1892 for publication in the *Proceedings* when submitting their paper to the *Transactions*.^{1,2}

By the late 1800s, a number of other ‘abstracting journals’ regularly published short summaries of scientific papers. Being effectively catalogues for scientific papers, these journals became important in promoting and communicating science, and journals began to ask authors to provide their own short summaries along with their papers.

In the 19th century, journals began to provide readers with summaries of articles published in other journals and in foreign languages. *Abstracts of Physical Papers from Foreign Sources* was started by the Physical Society of London in 1895. Likewise, in non-English-speaking

countries, such as Germany, journals were started in the mid-19th century that summarized international papers in many scientific disciplines for German-speaking readers.^{1,3} Because it was easier and more affordable to translate an abstract than the whole paper, abstracts became important in helping science to cross the linguistic barrier.⁴ In the early 20th century, efforts were made to standardize the length of abstracts to 300 words (for research articles in *The Lancet*’s journals, the length varies from 250 to 350 words). After World War 2, the Royal Society started to publish the abstract at the start of the article rather than separately in advance of the article.

Although the language in which science is primarily communicated has varied over time, by the early decades of the 20th century, German had become the lingua franca of the science community owing to the pre-eminence of German science.⁵ After the National Socialists came to power in 1933, many Jewish and Marxist scientists were expelled from universities, and there was a general exodus abroad (mostly to the UK and the USA). As a result, the émigré scientists started to publish in English, which has since taken over as the definitive worldwide lingua franca.⁵ Today, 98% of peer-reviewed scientific publishing is in English,^{6,7} which is also the official language of most scientific events and international and indexed academic journals.⁸ Although arguments can be made for a common scientific language,^{9,10} UNESCO, through its Recommendation on Open Science, has called on scientific institutions to foster multilingualism in the practice of science, in scientific publications, and in academic communications, to provide more equitable access to scientific knowledge.¹¹

Literature searches in the modern era

Abstracts, which are usually available for free, appear when searches are conducted using an

article search engine and are an essential part of literature searches. As a first step to making science communication more inclusive, there has been a recognition that articles published in non-English languages should include an abstract in English, and likewise, that articles published in English should include abstracts translated into a language relevant to the country of the article's origin. Translation of abstracts is already common practice for some scientific journals in bilingual or non-anglophone countries.⁸

Search engines rank articles according to relevance using algorithms that take into account a range of factors. Such algorithms are complex and the subject of study by search engine optimization experts and academics, aimed at understanding how the algorithms operate. There is evidence of bias in multilingual searches conducted in a well-known academic search engine, with documents published in languages other than English being systematically relegated to positions that make them less visible.¹²

In PubMed, the open-access search engine for life sciences and biomedical topics, language filters restrict a search to articles published in the selected language(s). Additional language filters can be added to a search. By default, PubMed displays English-language titles and abstracts when provided by the publisher. If supplied by the publisher, non-English abstracts can be accessed via a link from the English abstract display on the publisher's website.¹³

Although English is the native language of only 7.3% of the world's population and less than 20% can speak the language, nearly 75% of all scientific publications are in English.¹⁴ At *The Lancet*, which publishes in English, we recognized that we needed to make the research that we publish more inclusive through multilingualism and the establishment of best practices for equitable access.

Others have noted steps that could be taken to improve accessibility for non-English speakers including: the creation of linguistically diverse editorial boards focusing on the most commonly spoken languages to encourage publication in native languages; improving access to translation services, which could be discounted or free to scientists from low-income countries; encouraging duplicate publication in a second language of the authors' choosing, or as a supplement; reduced cost English language editing for non-English speakers; automatic translation of English articles to the desired language (and vice versa) for the end-user of the publisher's platform, making use of the rapidly improving Google Translate or other AI language technology; and adjustment of publication metrics to address the bias towards English language journals.¹⁴

Translating abstracts at The Lancet

Starting in early 2019 with the specialty journal, *The Lancet Global Health* (which publishes content including research, comments, and correspondence, focused on medical and health issues in disadvantaged populations across the globe), authors of research articles were informally offered the opportunity to publish a translation of their summary as an appendix. The uptake on this was about 20%–25% of accepted papers. As a result of interest from other journals within *The Lancet* group, a group was created with the goal of establishing a sustainable and resource-efficient way of expanding this into an official, *Lancet*-wide project.

The main features determined for the project were that the offer of a translated abstract should be made at the discretion of the editors-in-chief, particularly for manuscripts presenting research done in a non-Anglophone country or with potential global impact; that the translation should be the responsibility of the authors (who may

Figure 1. Workflow for publishing translated summaries for *Lancet* research articles; starting with the initial invitation, followed by reminders to the assistant editor and the author; the author is asked to do the translation after the correction of the first proofs.

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Supplementary appendix 1

This translation in French was submitted by the authors and we reproduce it as supplied. It has not been peer reviewed. *The Lancet's* editorial processes have only been applied to the original in English, which should serve as reference for this manuscript.

Cette traduction en français a été proposée par les auteurs et nous l'avons reproduite telle quelle. Elle n'a pas été examinée par des pairs. Les processus éditoriaux de *Lancet* n'ont été appliqués qu'à l'original en anglais, ce qui devrait servir de référence à ce manuscrit.

Supplement to: Lee EC, Chao DL, Lemaitre JC, et al. Achieving coordinated national immunity and cholera elimination in Haiti through vaccination: a modelling study. *Lancet Glob Health* 2020; 8: e1081-89.

Figure 2. The disclaimer page, which clarifies that the translation has not been peer reviewed or edited, and which appears as the first page of the translated summary.¹⁵

enlist assistance as deemed necessary); and published as an additional online appendix with minimal impact on regular manuscript workflow. The letter sent to the author with final manuscript revision requests includes this statement or similar: “We encourage the submission of translated summaries in languages that are relevant to the country where the research was done. We would be happy to publish your abstract in [LANGUAGE(S)]. Translated summaries are published unedited and unformatted, as a separate supplementary file. If you are interested in submitting a translation, please let me know. We will expect to receive the text once your manuscript is edited, at the proof stage. The final translated text should be of the final, edited summary, not the accepted version” (Figure 1). Publishing the translation in this way, simultaneously with the article, has the advantage that it avoids the need to request permission from the publisher; permission would be needed from the publisher to translate an abstract post-publication for subscription-based articles and open access articles published under a Creative Commons attribution non-commercial no derivatives (CC BY NC

ND) licence (which enables reusers to distribute the material in any medium or format, in unadapted form, for non-commercial purposes, as long as attribution is given to the creator).

A disclaimer page would be included, in both English and the language of the translation, stating that the translated abstract has not been through *The Lancet's* peer review or editorial processes (Figure 2). The translated abstract is treated as appendix 1; the regular appendix, which comprises supplementary material for the article, is included as appendix 2; both as PDFs. More than one translation may be accommodated, as long as they appear before the regular appendix and are numbered accordingly. (The native language(s) in question may relate to the authors, the setting, or both.) Labelling on both the PDF and HTML versions points to the translation(s) (Figure 3). The procedure necessarily trusts the accuracy of the translations, particularly for languages that use different characters, such as Chinese; however, it is acknowledged that this is a potential limitation of the approach. In addition, as

Figure 3. Translations are labelled on the pdf and may be reached via the links on the HTML version on the journal website.¹⁶

the appendix is in the form of an author-produced PDF, issues relating to typesetting foreign-language scripts are avoided. Publishing as an appendix, which is separate from the article, allows a straight translation of the final version of the abstract for which length is not an issue; any increases in length, which may result from wordier languages, should not be a problem. This relatively low-tech approach should be easy to adopt for smaller journals. Current machine translation tools use artificial neural networks combined with artificial intelligence-based techniques such as machine learning. Although we leave

authors to produce the translation, such tools may be used to provide a working draft.⁸

During the project build-up phase, the five-person project group (which included Assistant Editors and Senior Editors with additional languages) engaged with all of the Lancet Group's journals and consulted the production, assistant editor, e-production, and marketing teams. They created workflow documents (Figure 1) for all the teams involved and planned a pilot phase, which involved translation monitoring and troubleshooting of workflows.

The scheme was rolled out in the second half of 2019 to other *Lancet* journals at the discretion of their editors-in-chief. A Senior Assistant Editor with a supervisory role monitors the project on a day-to-day basis to ensure that our list of languages (now numbering 72) is kept up to date. Assistant Editors are asked to update the supervising editor when new translations are received. Workflow guidelines are available on a SharePoint page, but the supervising editor is also available to answer related queries as they arise. Feedback on the workflow guidelines is used to inform any amendments perceived as necessary; so far, only minor tweaks to the guidelines have been made. Data on the number of abstracts published, reader responses, and reasons for authors declining the opportunity to translate will be the subject of future review. Innovations to improve accessibility are being investigated, which are consistent with website integrity best practices.

Conclusion

There is an enhanced ethical drive within the international scientific community to increase inclusivity and diversity, which includes making science language accessible. In its approach, *The Lancet* aims to achieve equitable and inclusive partnerships by being transparent about how research engages with researchers, communities, and environments in countries of study. We believe that the translation of abstracts will improve access to, and visibility of, the research articles published by *The Lancet* for non-English researchers.

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